

USING AUDIO MATERIALS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AT DIFFERENT LEVELS OF LEARNERS (SONGS, AUDIO AND RADIO RECORDERS, RHYMES AND FILMS)

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the importance of using audio materials in English classes. Their role and effects in learning English at different ages.

Key words: audio and radio materials, different aged learners, feeling a sense of confidence, creating harmoniously developed, best method, source of motivation, listening skill, interaction.

It is not secret that a foreign language acquisition is core issue of today`s society of globalization. It has become a part of almost everyone in the world. Thus, to know a language is to know the world. Nowadays, much attention paid to teaching methods, to be more specific, what kinds of techniques are included while conducting lessons as most learners prefer various activities in class that lead to their motivation in participation during the study. Taking into the consideration that practice was accepted by the former president I.A. Karimov on December 10, signed a decree “On measures to further improvement of foreign language learning system”. It is emphasized that teaching and learning foreign languages would increase to a new stage in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

“On education” and “the National Program for training” in the country, an exhaustive foreign language teaching system, intended to creating harmoniously developed, well educated, modern thinking young generation, further integration of the country to the world community, has been created.

At the present time, using different methods in teaching English is very important. Particularly, the using of audio materials in teaching English at different

levels has grown rapidly because of the increasing emphasis on communicative techniques and it is obvious that the use of audio is a great help for foreign language teachers in stimulating and facilitating the target language. According to Wright many audio materials are useful for the language learners. That is to say, all audio materials have positive contributions to language learning as long as they are used at the right time, in the right place. One of the most appreciated materials applied to language learning and teaching is, of course, video. A recent large –scale survey by Canning – Wilson (2000) reveals that the students like learning language through the use of video, which is often used to mean quite different things in language teaching. Learning a foreign language better if they have more opportunities to be exposed to it. Another way they acquire a language is by using all their senses and by getting fully involved, by observing and copying sounds and gestures and by watching and listening. They also learn through exploring, experimenting, making mistakes and checking their understanding by repetition and also by feeling a sense of confidence. Finally, they feel motivated and learn better if a natural and stress free environment can be provided in the language class.

It is also generally believed that there is no single best method that meets the goals and needs of all learners and programs. Numerous methods have come and gone. We have seen the Audio – lingual Method, cognitive – based approaches, the Total Physical Response (TPR), the Natural Approach, and many others. In addition, the proficiency and standards – based movements have shaped the field with their attempts to define proficiency goals and thus have provided a general sense of direction. Some believe that foreign language instruction has finally come of age others refer to it as the post – method area. Although, the use of audio – visual method in language teaching has become a common fashion for the language teachers, many of them might not be well aware of the effectiveness of these. This research investigates how the language teachers, as well as learners, are benefitted from the audio materials in language teaching and learning. This research gives a

clear view of the reason of using audio materials in language teaching. Listening skill plays great role in using audio materials in teaching English.

Listening is one of the four fundamental skills through which a language is taught. It is one of the two skills that we use when communicating orally. According to Roost “Listening is an active process requiring participation on the part of the listener”. For example, when someone listens to a speaker, he or she processes the information mentally in order to construct an answer. During the listening process the listener is actively engaged. In learning a foreign language, it is important to listen to what is transmitted with a great deal of attention because this helps the listener to reproduce exactly, or almost exactly, what he or she hears. Therefore, listening is not an isolated skill, we listen in order to understand what has been heard. Moreover, the speaker and the listener must be interacting in a social context. According to Larsen – Freeman “It is through interaction between the speaker and the listener that the meaning becomes clear”. This clarity suggests an understanding of what has been heard.

Among the listening songs, rhymes, radio, recorder and films are the most effective ones to be used for learner in language class. Also they are fantastic materials for the language teachers to use with learners because of their unlimited benefits. songs being a source of motivation, interest and enjoyment. It is much easier for children to imitate and remember language than words which are just “spoken”. Again, a song or a chant can be used very effectively to teach children the sounds and rhythm of the language and to reinforce structures and vocabulary. Moreover, the songs contain words and expressions of high frequency and offer repetitions. The students are encouraged to actively involved in the learning process by making use of their musical knowledge . In this way the songs help students to develop confidence for language learning.

Many primary level language learners respond very well to rhymes. Rhymes are easy to learn and memorize. The children derive visible satisfaction and confidence from this new acquired “fluency” that comes so quickly.

Listening to radio is also very important to develop learners` listening skills. Because reciting a radio is easier than thinking, the learners discover control over new language and this new mastery can be utilized in everyday usage. The learners achieve an important new confidence in their ability to speak and communicate in English, most importantly, the learner learn several grammatical structure, sentence patterns, vocabulary words which can be used to give and get information.

When students are beginning English learners, the audio recorder is a vital tool for providing them with reviews of oral explanations and pronunciations of new material between lessons. Recording parts of the lessons is not just important for helping beginning students. It is also important to record parts of lessons when teaching intermediate and advanced new English learners. Although these young learners can initially find it very difficult to remember how to say complete phrases in a foreign language.

Action films captivate young students and help teachers convert their natural energy and enthusiasm into meaningful learning experiences. Action films also help even beginners associate words and phrases with meanings.

To sum up, by using audio aids in the classroom, teachers can teach languages making the class interesting. The results also indicate that music can be useful additional materials for teaching language. Teachers can use different English songs to teach listening skills. Teachers can also design listening activity using songs to test learners` listening skills. Audios make the language teaching and learning effective making.

USED LITERATURE:

1. Cakir, A. "Musical activities for young learners of EFL", 1999
2. Wilson – Christine Canning and Julie Wallace. "Practical aspects of Using Audio – Video in foreign language", Journal. 2000
3. Retrieved on February 20, 2007
4. Kashdan, S. "Using an Audio Recorder in Lessons for new English learners", 2006

5. Wright, A. "Audio – Visual Materials for the Language Teacher", Essex, Longman.